

REALISATION OF STRUCTURAL BATTERY COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces the concept of structural battery composite materials and their possible devices and the rationale for developing them. The paper presents an overview of the research performed in Sweden on a novel structural battery composite material. The research areas addressed include: carbon fibre electrodes, structural separators, multifunctional matrix materials, device architectures and material functionalization. Material characterization, fabrication and validation are also discussed. The paper focuses on a patented battery composite material technology. Here, carbon fibres are employed as combined negative battery electrodes and reinforcement, coated with a solid polymer electrolyte working simultaneously as electrolyte and separator with ability to transfer mechanical loads. The coated fibres are distributed in a conductive positive cathode material on an aluminium electron collector film. Efficient Li-ion transport between the electrodes is achieved by the solid polymer electrolyte coating being only a few hundred nanometres thick.

Finally some outstanding scientific and engineering challenges are discussed. Such challenges, calling for further research are related to manufacture, development of new solid polymer electrolytes for improved multifunctionality and the lack of material models.

1 INTRODUCTION

This paper reports on recent development of structural polymer composite lithium ion battery materials with intrinsic mechanical load bearing capability. Such *structural power composite material devices are desired for their potential to both provide the energy needs at reduced weight and increase safety of future electric vehicles*. In brief, adopting a multidisciplinary approach, a novel Li-ion battery material is developed employing commercial grades of carbon fibres as combined electrode and reinforcing elements and solid polymer electrolytes as the matrix for simultaneous Li-ion transport and transfer of mechanical loads. The materials developed are expected to significantly reduce vehicle system weight and allow electrical energy storage in the structural load path of future electric vehicles, in for example body-in-white as illustrated by Volvo Car Corporation in Figure 1.

In this paper we present an overview of the state-of-the-art and the current status of research performed in Sweden on structural battery composite materials. Furthermore, outstanding challenges for realisation of structural battery composites and their industrial implementation are discussed.

Figure 1: Illustration of the structural battery concept [https://www.media.volvocars.com].

2 STATE OF THE ART – STRUCTURAL BATTERY COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Structural battery composites have been studied for just over one decade. The most common approach to realize such multifunctional composites has been to embed thin-film batteries within composite laminates to create a multifunctional composite structure. Such structures have been developed with marine and aeronautical applications in mind; see e.g. [1-3]. An alternative strategy, which is pursued in this paper, is to develop composite materials with intrinsic multifunctional capability. Research to realise such structural battery composites has been reviewed in detail in a recent paper by Asp and Greenhalgh [4]. In summary, structural battery composite materials rely on chemical redox reactions in the solid materials, i.e. in the carbon fibre electrodes and the cathode-doped polymer electrolyte matrix material, and efficient lithium ion transportation between the phases via a solid-state electrical insulator. In this section, a brief overview of the state-of-the-art on structural battery composite materials and their constituents is presented.

2.1 Carbon fibre electrodes

Different types of graphitised carbons have been used as the negative electrode in secondary lithium-ion batteries. Carbon is used for its ability to intercalate lithium ions. The theoretical capacity of graphite is 372 mAh/g [5]. Commercially available carbon fibres are produced for structural applications by maximising their high specific stiffness and strength. The combined high specific mechanical properties and ability to intercalate lithium ions suggest that such carbon fibres can be used as electrode-reinforcement in structural battery composite materials. The electrochemical performance of commercially available carbon fibres has therefore been studied [5-7]. From these works it is evident that a number of commercially available carbon fibres provide excellent electrochemical performance. The multifunctional properties for one of these fibre types, the intermediate modulus fibre IMS65 by Toho Tenax, are presented in Table 1.

Property	Unit	Value
<i>Stiffness (tension)</i>	[GPa]	290
<i>Tensile strength</i>	[GPa]	6.00
<i>Electrical resistivity</i>	[Ω cm $\times 10^{-3}$]	1.45
<i>Reversible capacity (heavy tow at 1C)</i>	[mAh/g]	129
<i>Reversible capacity (single fibre at C/2)</i>	[mAh/g]	250

Table 1: Multifunctional properties for unsized IMS65 carbon fibres, from [5, 6].

In the table, the reversible capacity (10th charge cycle) is reported alongside with mechanical properties and electrical resistivity for the fibre. This capacity is measured at relatively high currents,

i.e. high charge rates, the heavy tow electrode (24,000 fibres) is charged at a rate that would fully charge the theoretical capacity in 1 hour, whereas the capacity of a single IMS65 carbon fibre is measured at C/2 (i.e. full charge in two hours). There is a conspicuous effect of the fibre yarn on the electrochemical capacity of the CF electrode. The lower capacity for fibres in a tow compared to a single fibre is explained by the difficulty to access and intercalate fibres internally in the tow. From these results it is concluded that there will be great benefit in using individual fibres in batteries compared to using yarns [4].

The effect of electrical charging and discharging on the mechanical performance of carbon fibres has been studied by Jacques et al. [8, 9]. They showed tensile stiffness to be unaffected by the lithiation and delithiation of carbon fibres, for all investigated fibre types. In contrast, they found a reduction in the ultimate tensile strength of approximately 20% after the first lithiation. However, at subsequent delithiation strength was partly recovered, and the residual ultimate tensile strength of the delithiated fibre reported was approximately 10% lower than that of the pristine fibre. Furthermore, swelling associated with charging of the fibre was reported by Jacques et al. [10]. Swelling in the axial direction up to 1% was reported as the measured capacity approached the theoretical limit for graphite. Similarly, swelling in the radial direction up to 8% was reported when fully charged. Effects on the internal stress state in the composite from the swelling and shrinkage of the electrodes during electrochemical cycling must be considered in design. To the authors' knowledge no such methods have yet been developed.

2.2 Solid Polymer Electrolyte (SPE) matrix

Regarding the matrix, the challenge for structural batteries is to achieve both high stiffness and Li-ion conductivity. This dual character is needed to secure high mechanical performance and power and energy densities for the composite. To achieve these multiple capabilities of the composite solid polymer electrolytes are preferred since liquid electrolytes cannot carry and transfer any mechanical load to the carbon fibres. However, the ion conductivity is low in SPEs, typically at best three orders of magnitude lower than for liquid electrolytes. Consequently, structural power composite designs must either be made considering the relatively low Li-ion conductivity of the SPE or new improved SPEs must be developed. On the other hand, the low conductivity can be mitigated by minimising the SPE thickness by careful design of the architecture, as discussed below.

Figure 2. Co-polymerisation of polyethylene glycol (200) dimethacrylate and methoxy polyethylene glycol (550) monomethacrylate (Left); Ionic conductivity versus storage modulus at room temperature for different mixing ratios of SR209/CD552, from [12] (Right).

Studies on multifunctional SPEs for structural batteries have been performed by at ARL in the US [11], at Swerea SICOMP [12] and at KTH [13] employing block co-polymers containing ethylene oxide (EO) groups in polymer networks processed by thermo- or UV-curing. By changing the cross-linking density in relation to the EO groups they were able to tailor the stiffness to ion conductivity ratio of the SPE. For this purpose two monomers were mixed, a dimethacrylate for mechanical properties and a monomethacrylate for Li-ion conductivity, both containing EO-groups as illustrated in

Figure 2, were employed to graft highly conductive chains on to a structural, three-dimensional polymer network. The effect of monomer mixing ratios on the polymer electrolyte multifunctional performance is plotted in Figure 2. Multifunctional performance was judged by the combined lithium ion conductivity and storage modulus. The figure shows that all copolymers exhibited enhanced multifunctional behaviour relative to the baseline, represented by the linear fit of the performance of the homopolymers. The SPEs were polymerised in the presence of a lithium salt. Willgert et al. [13] showed in their studies that the salt did not impair curing of the SPE and that there was no significant effect of salt concentration on conductivity. Recently, researchers at KTH demonstrated that the addition of small amounts of thiol-ene (an organosulfur compound) increases the lithium ion conductivity of the solid poly(ethylene-oxide)-methacrylate electrolytes discussed above without compromising their stiffness, further improving their multifunctional performance [14].

Leijonmarck et al. [15] developed a method to coat individual carbon fibres in a fibre roving with a thin solid polymer electrolyte from the methacrylate monomers presented above. Via this approach a few hundred nanometres thick, defect free [16], SPE coating resulted. Consequently, the procedure can be applied to compensate the relatively low ion conductivity of the SPE by reducing the ion transport distance to a few hundred nanometres. The SPE coating was deposited onto carbon fibres by electrochemical polymerisation. From this coating process, an SPE coating resulted on all fibres in a roving. Its thickness was shown to depend on the monomer as well as salt concentration in the solution. Figure 3 shows an uncoated, unsized, IMS65 fibre next to a coated IMS65 fibre. The average coating thickness, determined by Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was found to be 470 nm. As a result of the electrocoating process, where Li-triflate was used as a supporting electrolyte, the achieved SPE coating contained a sufficient amount of Li-triflate salt to allow for use as a battery electrolyte without any further post-processing. The coating is also electrically insulating, hence allowing the cathode to be brought in direct contact with the coated fibre. The mechanical integrity of these coatings is demonstrated in an accompanying study [17].

Figure 3. Uncoated IMS65 (left) and block copolymer SPE coated IMS65 fibres (right).

2.3 Material architecture

The need for high energy and power density has immediate implication on the architectural designs of structural battery materials. The obvious choice is to exploit the laminated material configuration of composites and traditional batteries. The first ever structural battery composite was made by this approach by Wetzel et al. [18]. The laminated composite battery consisted of a metal mesh coated with a cathode material, a carbon fibre fabric acting as an anode, a fibre glass separator layer, and a structural solid polymer electrolyte binding the components. In this design the cathode coated mesh and the carbon fibre electrodes both carry load and are electrically conductive current collectors. The fibre glass separator provides additional structural support, whilst enduring electrical isolation of the electrode layers. The polymer electrolyte transfer load to the other components while simultaneously conducting ions between electrodes. The material suffered from poor mechanical performance and did not function as a battery due to poor electrical insulation. Following the approach by Wetzel and co-workers numerous laminated structural battery designs have been suggested, all with no or poor electrochemical performance [4]. One problem with the laminated design is the relatively thick glass separator ($>100 \mu\text{m}$), which is much thicker than separators used for traditional battery designs (which

are typically 30 μm thick). Given to low ion conductivity of the SPE high ohmic losses result from this design. For this design approach to be competitive, a separator thickness of less than 500 nm is required [4].

A three-dimensional battery design was developed at Swerea SICOMP and KTH which allows for significantly reduced Li-ion transport. In addition, the design employs single carbon fibres as negative electrodes. The 3D battery design is expected to allow faster charge rates as the single carbon fibre charge faster than fibres in a tow, as described above. A schematic illustration of the patented 3D carbon fibre battery material [19] is shown in Figure 4. In this concept thousands of carbon fibres coated with a with a few hundred nanometre thick sheath of the solid polymer electrolyte (SPE) are distributed in a cathode doped matrix. By the combined Li-ion conductivity and electrical insulating characteristics of the SPE the coated fibres are allowed to be brought into contact with the cathode.

Figure 4: Schematic illustration of the cross-section of the 3d carbon fibre battery.

3 THE SPE COATED CARBON FIBRE BATTERY

In this Section details on the coated CF battery technology are presented. To date, two different routes have been pursued: a 2D-battery set up using coated fibres in a spread tow stacked on a cathode film and a 3D semi-structural battery design with coated carbon fibres surrounded by a cathode matrix. Procedures for coating of individual carbon fibres in a yarn, and the effects of different parameters like coating potential, monomer and salt concentrations have been presented elsewhere [15] and are not further discussed in this paper.

3.1 2D flexible CF battery with soft SPE coatings

A two-dimensional coated carbon fibre battery concept is developed for non- or semi-structural applications, employing a fairly soft SPE coating on fibres in a spread tow. The first designs have been targeted for realisation of a flexible battery, i.e. a battery device that can be bent.

The 2D CF battery is made as illustrated in Figure 5. The carbon fibres are electrocoated with a thin sheath of solid polymer electrolyte as described by Leijonmarck et al. [15]. The coated fibres are kept strained in a PTFE holder (i.e. rig) fixating the yarn (12k). A cathode film is applied on the coated fibres yarn and a liquid electrolyte (ethylene carbonate and diethyl carbonate mixture) is applied to enhance electrochemical performance. By this approach the SPE coated section of the carbon fibre yarn is brought in direct contact with the cathode film. Alternatively, a thin glass fibre separator is positioned between the coated fibre yarn and the cathode film [15]. Here Li-metal is used as counter electrode. In this set-up no additional electron connectors are required. The uncoated section of the carbon fibres are directly connected in the circuit as is the Li-metal.

A battery was made from IMS65 fibres coated with a SPE from 40% of the mono-functional and 60% of the di-functional monomers, i.e. the 40:60 SPE illustrated in the conductivity/modulus plot in Figure 2. The fibres were brought in direct contact with the Li-metal as illustrated in Figure 5, and the battery was soaked in liquid electrolyte and closed in an Al/polymer bag. The battery was cycled at

low currents with a specific capacity of approximately 250 mAh/g. The measured capacity is close to the capacity measured for the battery set-up with a softer – more ionically conductive SPE, employing a glass fibre separator, previously reported by Leijonmarck et al. [15].

Figure 5: Schematic illustration of the assembly (left) of the 2D CF battery (right).

Preliminary trials to assess the performance of the 2D battery during flexural loading have not yet been performed. However, tests on coated carbon fibres exposed to tensile fatigue have been performed and are reported in an accompanying paper by Leijonmarck et al. [17]. Results from these tests show that the coating does not damage during fatigue.

3.2 3D semi-structural battery

Carlson and co-workers [20] prepared a semi-structural 3D carbon fibre battery cell, illustrated in Figure 4. The battery is made from a roving of approximately 1,000 SPE coated carbon fibres. The roving was electrocoated with an SPE and dried according to the procedures described by Leijonmarck et al. [15]. The coating was polymerised in a PTFE rig from the monofunctional SR550 monomer supplied by Sartomer, leaving grafted polymer chains on the individual fibres. The battery was built under argon atmosphere, where coated fibres made up a structure containing electrode material, current collector and a thin polymer separator/electrolyte. The rig, containing the coated CFs, was attached to an aluminium sheet (current collector), in such a way that the coated CFs were in contact with the metal. A slurry consisting of LiFePO_4 :Super-P carbon:PVDF 54:34:12 by weight in DMF was applied onto the SPE coated carbon fibre yarn, where after the DMF was evaporated leaving a positive electrode introduced in close contact with both the coated carbon fibres and the aluminium current collector.

The 3D battery was exposed to electrical cycling, at $C/5$. The capacity of the battery was at best 60 % of the used LiFePO_4 (102 mAh/g compared to theoretically 170 mAh/g). Thus, the result is very encouraging. However, the current battery concept can only carry tensile loads parallel to the fibres. Significant work must be performed to make a solid surrounding cathode material, which is needed to make the battery structural for general load cases. For this purpose, methods to realize solid polymer electrolyte matrix materials with well-dispersed cathode material, e.g. LiFePO_4 , and electrically conducting material, e.g. carbon black, to be distributed around the coated fibres must be developed.

The proposed 3D battery technology allows the designer to vary the specific capacity of the material. The amount, and hence the weight of the current collector can be minimised by increasing the battery height, as illustrated in Figure 6. Exploiting the full capacity of the carbon fibres, balancing the amount of cathode material in the surrounding matrix material, can theoretically reach a volumetric energy density up to 700 Wh/l when using LiFePO_4 as positive electrode material. However, as the energy density increases the power density decreases, the actual energy density will likely be lower. A minimum specific energy of the material of 200 Wh/kg is forecasted.

Figure 6. Theoretical energy density of a tow of 24,000 carbon fibres surrounded by cathode material (LiFePO₄) in relation to the width of the current collector.

4 CHALLENGES FOR REALISATION OF STRUCTURAL BATTERY COMPOSITES

Scientific and engineering challenges for realisation and industrialisation of structural battery composites and their structures have been discussed in detail by Asp and Greenhalgh [4, 21]. The three most urgent outstanding challenges, as identified by the authors, are discussed below.

4.1 Multifunctional SPEs and cathode material doped SPEs

Perhaps the most challenging aspect of this research field is that of the matrix/solid polymer electrolyte (SPE) development since the mechanical and electrical demands are strongly in conflict. This challenge is illustrated in Figure 7. In the figure a shaded area has been included to indicate desired properties of the polymer electrolytes for high performance structural power materials. Any modification of the constituents to enhance one function leads to a significant reduction in the other function. In fact, for the systems studied to date there appears to be a strong detrimental interaction between these functionalities, such that the behaviour falls well below a simple rule of mixtures.

Figure 7. Schematic of the ion conductivity versus stiffness for solid polymer electrolytes [22].

Shirshova et al. [23] suggested route forward to overcome this conflict for SPEs is to develop so called interpenetrating polymer networks (IPNs), comprising a structural polymer backbone filled with a liquid electrolyte or an ionic liquid for high ion conductivity. Clearly this presents significant practical difficulties, particularly since the introduction of reinforcement fibres leads to a different matrix microstructure from that in the bulk condition. Therefore is a need to have better control over this microstructure during processing and perhaps even pursuing completely different curing

chemistries. There are considerable research opportunities here for novel matrix formulations that extend beyond the current suite of monofunctional polymer systems used in conventional composites.

Finally, to realise a structural battery a cathode must be made with these solid polymer electrolytes in a subsequent step. In the case of the 3D carbon fibre battery this implies that the cathode material, e.g. LiFePO_4 , which comes as a powder with dimensions of 50-100 nm, must be dispersed in the SPE together with an electrically conductive substance, e.g. carbon black. Dispersion and subsequent impregnation of the fibre system with this material poses great challenges. For this reason alternative methods, e.g. deposition methods or coating methods, for the application of the mechanically robust cathode must be developed.

4.2 Multiphysics/multiscale models

There is a concern that swelling and shrinkage of the electrodes due to intercalation of lithium ions may cause damage to the composite. Damage is expected to decrease the mechanical properties of the structural battery and reduce its charging properties through impaired ion diffusivity between phases or even exfoliation of graphite layers in the fibres. Crack propagation and possible damage evolution, e.g. exfoliation of graphite layers in the carbon fibre, have been analysed numerically by Pupurs and Varna [24]. Through this first attempt, employing FE-analysis, the crack geometry was predicted to depend on the ion concentration distribution and the elastic stress distribution in the fibre and surrounding polymer electrolyte. Research is called for, extending the approach taken by Pupurs and Varna [24] to address carbon fibre structural battery material architectures employing a multi-physics approach considering ion-diffusion controlled swelling and shrinkage in combination with mechanical loads inherent to thermal shrinkage during manufacture and mechanical in-service loads. Experimental proof of predicted volume changes and damage formation at the material interfaces (i.e. debonding) from electrochemical cycling and mechanical loading is also needed.

Access to such models is a prerequisite for the development of efficient and robust design methods for structural battery composites. No such method exists today.

4.3 Fabrication

The manufacture of composite components has always been the critical step in their utilisation. Manufacturing defects often limit particular designs. For structural battery materials, there are significant hurdles which still need to be addressed, and scale-up of these materials poses a major challenge.

Perhaps the most critical aspect is the need to fabricate in a moisture-free environment (i.e. as least less than 50 PPM water). Conventional composite manufacture rarely is concerned with maintaining a dry environment; this is usually ambient. The conventional battery industry, however, is well equipped for fabricating in moisture-free environments, but these devices are usually relatively small (as compared to load-bearing structures) and any coatings/barrier materials are not anticipated to need to withstand structural loads. Furthermore, when mechanically loaded, structures deform, in some instances significantly; therefore, any structural battery material would need to have barrier layers which are robust enough to withstand any mechanical loading.

To scale-up manufacturing of structural battery materials, combinations of state-of-the-art composite and battery manufacturing technologies must be considered. The multifunctional parts must then be introduced in a structure or system. Understanding and developing cost efficient dry environment manufacturing of structural battery materials with the aim to scale-up in at least semi-continuous production is needed since none of these technologies currently exist.

A particular issue which is not a concern for conventional composite fabrication is that of contact between the electrodes. Even a single conducting (carbon fibre) bridging between the electrodes can be enough to short circuit the device and loss of electrical performance. This issue is exacerbated by the need to have as short distance as possible between the electrodes, to ensure good power densities, as discussed above.

9 CONCLUSIONS

Structural battery materials have been identified as possible means to realise competitive electric road vehicles. Introduction of an intrinsic energy storage capability in car structures materials provides a route to significantly reduce weight of future electric vehicles. Research to develop structural batteries has been performed in the US and Europe over the last decade. As a result, structural battery concepts have emerged with potentially high specific energy densities. In particular, commercially available carbon fibres have demonstrated excellent electrochemical performance with specific capacities approaching those of commercial electrode materials. Carbon fibres also feature high electrical conductivity. Multifunctional solid polymer electrolytes have been developed. However, more work is needed to realise more competitive solid polymer electrolytes. In particular, research is recommended to develop novel interpenetrating polymer network materials to achieve stiffer matrix materials with improved ion conductivity. Furthermore, methods to introduce, distribute and disperse cathode materials in 3D carbon fibre battery composites are needed. Access to such methods, and development of engineering manufacturing techniques, will allow up-scaling of manufacturing processes for these materials. Finally, design methods, considering phenomena such as swelling and shrinkage of material constituents, must be developed for successful introduction of structural batteries in industrial applications.

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REFERENCES

- [1] T. Pereira, Z. Guo, S. Nieh, J. Arias, H.T. Hahn, Embedding thin-film lithium energy cells in structural composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **68**, 2008, pp. 1935-1941.
- [2] S. Roberts, G. Aglietti, Satellite multi-functional power structure: Feasibility and mass savings, *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part G: Journal of Aerospace Engineering*, **222**, 2008, pp. 41-51.
- [3] J. Thomas, S. Qidwai, Mechanical design and performance of composite multifunctional materials, *Acta Materialia*, **52**, 2004; pp. 2155-2164.
- [4] L.E. Asp and E.S. Greenhalgh, Structural power composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **101**, 2014, pp. 41-61.
- [5] M.H. Kjell, E. Jacques, D. Zenkert, M. Behm, G. Lindbergh, PAN-based carbon fiber negative electrodes for structural lithium-ion batteries, *Journal of the Electrochemical Society*, **158**, 2011, pp. A1473-1481.
- [6] M.H. Kjell, T.G. Zavalis, M. Behm, G. Lindbergh, Electrochemical characterization of lithium intercalation processes of PAN-based carbon fibers in a microelectrode system, *Journal of the Electrochemical Society*, **160**, 2013, pp. A1455-A1460.
- [7] J.F. Snyder, E.L. Wong, C.W. Hubbard, Evaluation of commercially available carbon fibers, fabrics, and papers for potential use in multifunctional energy storage applications, *Journal of the Electrochemical Society*, **156**, 2009; pp. A215-A224.
- [8] E. Jacques, M.H. Kjell, D. Zenkert, G. Lindbergh, M. Behm, M. Willgert, Impact of electrochemical cycling on the tensile properties of carbon fibres for structural lithium-ion composite batteries, *Composites Science and Technology*, 2012; **72**, pp. 792-798.
- [9] E. Jacques, M.H. Kjell, D. Zenkert, G. Lindbergh, M. Behm, Impact of mechanical loading on electrochemical performance of carbon fibres, *Proc. 18th Int. Conf. on Composite Materials*, Jeju, South Korea, 2011.
- [10] E. Jacques, M.H. Kjell, D. Zenkert, G. Lindbergh, M. Behm, Expansion of carbon fibres induced by lithium intercalation for structural electrode applications, *Carbon*, **59**, 2013, pp. 246-254.

- [11] J.F. Snyder, R.H. Carter, E.D. Wetzel, Electrochemical and mechanical behavior in mechanically robust solid polymer electrolytes for use in multifunctional structural batteries, *Chemistry of Materials*, **19**, 2007, pp. 3793–3801
- [12] M. Wysocki, L.E. Asp, S. Ekstedt, Structural polymer electrolyte for use in multifunctional energy storage devices, *Proceedings of ECCM14*, Budapest, Hungary, 2010.
- [13] M. Willgert, M.H. Kjell, E. Jacques, M. Behm, G. Lindbergh, M. Johansson, Photoinduced free radical polymerization of thermoset lithium battery electrolytes, *European Polymer Journal*, **47**, 2011, pp.2732–2738.
- [14] M. Willgert, M.H. Kjell, G. Lindbergh, M. Johansson, *Solid State Ionics*, **236**, 2013, pp. 22–29.
- [15] S. Leijonmarck, T. Carlson, G. Lindbergh, L.E. Asp, H. Maples, A. Bismarck, Solid polymer electrolyte coated carbon fibres for structural and novel micro batteries, *Composites Science and Technology*, **89**, 2013, pp. 149-157.
- [16] S. Leijonmarck, A. Mathew, K. Oksman, G. Lindbergh, L.E. Asp. Direct electropolymerization of polymer electrolytes onto carbon fibres - A route to structural batteries? *Proceedings of the 16th European Conference on Composite Materials ECCM 16*, Seville, Spain, 2014.
- [17] S. Leijonmarck, A. Pupurs, L.E. Asp, G. Lindbergh and J. Varna, Strength of thin solid polymer electrolyte coatings and the coated carbon fibres, *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Composite Materials ICCM20*, Copenhagen, Denmark, 2015.
- [18] E.D. Wetzel. Reducing weight: Multifunctional composites integrate power, communications, and structure, *AMPTIAC Q*, **8**, 2004, pp. 91–95.
- [19] Asp LE, Bismarck A, Carlson T, Lindbergh G, Leijonmarck S, Kjell M. A battery half-cell, a battery and their manufacture, PCT Intl Appl. No. PCT/EP2013/068024, 2013.
- [20] T. Carlson, Multifunctional composite materials – Design, manufacture and experimental characterisation. Doctoral Thesis, Luleå University of Technology, Sweden, ISSN: 1402-1544, Luleå, 2013.
- [21] L.E. Asp and E.S. Greenhalgh, Multi-functional composites for load bearing and electrical power storage, Ed. K. Friedrich, Elsevier, in print.
- [22] L.E. Asp, Multifunctional composite materials for energy storage in structural load paths, *Plastics, Rubber and Composites: Macromolecular Engineering*, **42**, 2013, pp. 144-149.
- [23] N. Shirshova, A. Bismarck, S. Carreyette, Q.P.V. Fontana, E.S. Greenhalgh, P. Jacobsson, P. Johansson, M.J. Marczewski, J. Scheers, G. Kalinka, A. Kucernak, M.S.P. Shaffer, J.H.G. Steinke, M. Wienrich. Structural Electrolytes for Supercapacitors Based on Ionic Liquid Doped Epoxy Resins, *Journal of Materials Chemistry*, **48**, 2013, pp. 15300-15309.
- [24] A. Pupurs, J. Varna, Modeling mechanical stress and exfoliation damage in carbon fiber electrodes subjected to cyclic intercalation/deintercalation of lithium ions, *Composites Part B*, **65**, 2014, pp. 69-79.